

EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF OREOSELONE. PART I.

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Fries migration of *isovaleroyloxy*-7-hydroxycoumarin gives largely 8-acyl derivative. β -Resorcylic acid, on condensation with malic acid, gives 7-hydroxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid and 5-hydroxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid which can be separated after methylation. 7-Hydroxycoumarin-6-carboxylic chloride condenses with ethyl *isopropyl* malonate and ethyl *isopropyl* cyanacetate but the products resist ring-closure to a coumaranone.

Spath, Klager and Schlosser (*Ber.*, 1931, 64, 2203) published a preliminary investigation on oreoselone, a fish poison. In a later paper (*ibid.*, 1933, 66, 749) the structure (I) was advanced on the basis of its degradation to 7-hydroxycoumarin.

Therefore, oreoselone belongs to the psoralene group of furocoumarins.

Yamashita (*Sci. Repts. Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1935, 24, 205) prepared 2-*isopropyl*-6-hydroxycoumaranone but could not transform it to oreoselone. We have also failed to convert 6-hydroxycoumaranone to a coumarin with malic acid.

Therefore we directed our attention to the Fries migration of 7-*isovaleroyloxy*coumarin (II, R=H). The product is 7-hydroxy-8-*isovaleroyl*coumarin.

Minute amounts of 6-acyl derivative were also formed. Fries migration of 7-*omega*-chloro-*isovaleroyloxy*coumarin (II, R=Cl) was not successful (*cf.* however, Row and Seshadri *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1940, 11A, 206 who synthesised coumarino-7 : 8-furanones by the Fries migration of the chloroacetyl derivative).

Clayton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 525) found that carboxy, carbomethoxy and aceto group in the 4-position of the resorcinol molecule inhibited Pechmann condensation. But Shah, Sethna, Banerjee and Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 714) found that methyl β -resorcylate reacted with ethyl acetoacetate. They confirmed that 4-acyl group inhibited the reaction. 7-Hydroxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (*cf.* Arama,

Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan, 1924, 4, 113), as prepared from β -resorcylic acid, is accompanied by small quantities of an isomeric substance. The two have been separated after methylation. From the completely methylated product, 7-methoxy-6-carbomethoxycoumarin (m.p. 172°) is easily isolated. From the mother-liquors an isomeric product (m.p. 121-22°) is obtained. This substance on demethylation gives an acid (violet ferric reaction) which on decarboxylation furnishes 5-hydroxycoumarin. Hence this isomeric product is 5-hydroxy-6-carboxycoumarin (VI). This is reminiscent of the observation of Sethna, Shah and Shah (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 228) who found methyl β -resorcylate to give 5-hydroxy-6-carbomethoxycoumarin derivatives when anhydrous aluminium chloride was used in anhydrous ether. Therefore, it appears that aluminium chloride is not peculiar in that it induces only this type of condensation and in the formulation of any theory regarding the formation of 5-hydroxycoumarins by aluminium chloride, this fact has to be taken into account.

7-Hydroxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid has been converted into 7-methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid. The acid chloride of the latter (V) reacts with ethyl sodio-*isopropyl* malonate under pressure to give (IV, R=CO₂Et),

but the substance could not be hydrolysed smoothly. All attempts to hydrolyse it resulted in its breakdown to 7-hydroxy-6-carboxycoumarin.

4-Cyanacetoresorcinol dimethyl ether (Sonn, *Ber.*, 1918, 51, 823) is smoothly converted into 6-methoxycoumaranone (Blom and Tambor, *Ber.*, 1905, 38, 3590) by the elimination of methyl cyanide but the condensation product of ethyl *isopropyl* cyanacetate with the chloride of 7-methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (IV, R=CN) does not give an analogous coumaranone, a complex substance being formed. The product (IV, R=CN) could not also be satisfactorily demethylated.

The compound (V) reacts with *isobutyl* zinc iodide and a product (m.p. 87-89°) is obtained which does not analyse for the expected ketone. This substance may be slightly impure *isobutyl* ester (m.p. 99-101°) mixed with which it has m.p. 87-90° and with which its analytical results correspond.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenylisobutyl Ketone.—To a solution of resorcinol dimethyl ether (12.8 c.c.) in carbon bisulphide (12.8 c.c.) powdered aluminium chloride (10.5 g.) was added. *iso*Valeroyl chloride (14.8 c.c.), dissolved in carbon bisulphide (12 c.c.), was added gradually with shaking. The mixture was ultimately refluxed till the evolution of hydrogen chloride ceased. After removal of the solvent the reaction mixture was decomposed with ice and extracted with ether. The product has b.p. 165°/4 mm., yield 60%.

The *phenylhydrazone* crystallised from dilute alcohol in fine needles, m.p. 85°. (Found : N, 9.32. $C_{13}H_{22}O_2N_2$ requires N, 9.39 per cent).

Bromination of the above ketone in acetic acid solution furnished an oil which, when boiled with sodium acetate in alcoholic solution, gave a product, m.p. 113° after crystallisation from acetic acid. This substance (Found : C, 43.21 ; H, 5.43 per cent) was not a coumaranone.

Methylation of 2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenylisobutyl Ketone in acetone solution with Dimethyl Sulphate.—A mixture of the ketone (26 g.) dissolved in acetone (90 c.c.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (50 g.) was refluxed on the steam-bath with dimethyl sulphate (21 c.c.) for 4 hours. After addition of water, the semi-solid product was stirred with dilute alcohol when it solidified. After crystallisation from alcohol it had m.p. 145-46°. (Found : C, 71.7 ; H, 8.03 per cent). It is the condensation product of 2 mols. of the methylated ketone with 1 mol. of acetone and has the structure

Condensation of Benzoylglycollonitrile with Resorcinol : Formation of ω -Benzoyloxyresacetophenone.—To an ice-cold mixture of benzoylglycollonitrile (5.8 g.), resorcinol (4 g.), zinc chloride (7.7 g.), dry ether (40 c.c.), a stream of dry hydrogen chloride was passed till the originally separated oily layer solidified. After standing in an ice-bath for 12 hours, the mixture was decomposed and ether distilled off. After heating with water, the product was collected and crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 200°, yield 6.2 g. (Found : C, 66.13 ; H, 4.38. $C_{15}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 66.18 ; H, 4.41 per cent).

ω -Benzoyloxyresacetophenone did not condense with ethyl acetoacetate or malic acid under the usual conditions.

6-Methoxycoumaranone (Blom and Tambor, *loc. cit.*) could not be alkylated with isopropyl iodide in the presence of sodium ethoxide or sodamide.

6-Methoxycoumaranone (1 g.) in acetone (10 c.c.) was refluxed with potassium hydroxide solution (5 c.c. of 5%) for 10 minutes. The product separated and was crystallised from hot benzene, m.p. 210°. (Found : C, 68.18 ; H, 5.67. $C_{21}H_{20}O_6$ requires C, 68.48 ; H, 5.43 per cent). This is obviously the condensation product of two molecules of the coumaranone with one of acetone. Similarly ethylmethyl ketone gave a condensation product, m.p. 195° after crystallisation from benzene. (Found : C, 69.1 ; H, 5.76. $C_{22}H_{22}O_6$ requires C, 68.81 ; H, 6.17 per cent). The condensation with aromatic aldehydes was monomolecular; *benzylidene*, m.p. 145° (Found : C, 75.93 ; H, 5.23. Calc. C, 76.19 ; H, 4.76 per cent); *piperonylidene*, m.p. 187° (Found : C, 68.8 ; H, 4.37. $C_{11}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 68.9 ; H, 4.05 per cent); *veratrylidene*, m.p. 185° (Found : C, 69.43 ; H, 5.23. $C_{18}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 69.23 ; H, 5.12 per cent); *o-nitrobenzylidene*, m.p. 199-200° (Found : N, 5.01. $C_{16}H_{11}O_5N$ requires N, 4.71 per cent); *6-nitropiperonylidene*, m.p. 250° (decomp.). (Found : N, 4.09. $C_{17}H_{11}O_7N$ requires N, 4.06 per cent). 6-Methoxycoumaranones were prepared with either aqueous sodium hydroxide solution or with a few drops of concentrated hydrochloric acid.

Fries Migration of 7-isoValeroyloxycoumarin: Formation of 7-Hydroxy-8-isovalerocoumarin.—A solution of 7-hydroxycoumarin (1 g.) in pyridine (0.6 c.c.) (dissolved by warming) was treated dropwise in the ice-cold with isovaleryl chloride (1 c.c.). The mixture was finally warmed for 5 minutes with stirring. After decomposition with ice, the precipitated solids (after drying) were crystallised from petroleum ether, m.p. 68°. (Found: C, 68.29; H, 5.79. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 68.29; H, 5.69 per cent). The foregoing 7-isovaleroyloxycoumarin (33 g.) and powdered aluminium chloride (7.5 g.) were heated for 45 minutes at 70-75°, for 45 minutes at 120° and finally for 30 minutes at 135°. After decomposition with ice, the residue was extracted with ether. From the ethereal solution the ketone formed was recovered. The product crystallised from 50% alcohol (oxime, m.p. 168°). (Found: C, 68.53; H, 5.69. $C_{14}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 68.29; H, 5.69 per cent). The acetyl derivative of the ketone had m.p. 93° after crystallisation from petroleum ether. (Found: C, 67.0; H, 5.59. $C_{16}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 66.67; H, 5.55 per cent). The ketone did not give any colour with ferric chloride and hence was concluded to be the 8-isovalero derivative (*cf.* Ray, Silooja and Vaid, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 813).

α -Chloroisovaleroyl derivative of 7-hydroxycoumarin, prepared in the usual way, had m.p. 77° (ex. petroleum ether). (Found: C, 60.29; H, 4.77. $C_{14}H_{13}O_4Cl$ requires C, 59.89; H, 4.63 per cent). Fries migration of this substance was not successful under all conditions tried.

7-Hydroxycoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid.—The following modification gave double the yield obtained by Arama (*loc. cit.*). Concentrated sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) was added to a mixture of β -resorcylic acid (5 g.), malic acid (4.5 g.) and the mixture left overnight. After heating at 110° for 3-4 hours, it was poured on to crushed ice when a pasty mass separated which, however, solidified on scratching. After crystallisation from alcohol the mixture had m.p. 265-72°. Arama (*loc. cit.*) gives m.p. 244-62° depending on the rate of heating. The mixture, m.p. 265-72°, (3 g.) dissolved in dry acetone (100 c.c.) was mixed with potassium carbonate (anhydrous, 12 g.) and treated with dimethyl sulphate (purified, 6 c.c.) in small quantities at a time, the whole thing being kept under reflux. An intense yellow colour developed after a short interval and as the methylation proceeded, it became fainter and fainter and ultimately disappeared, the whole operation taking about 4-5 hours. After removal of acetone by distillation, water was added and the residue collected. It was crystallised from alcohol when the first crop, m.p. 172° (yield 1.5 g.) separated. (Found: C, 61.47; H, 4.34. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 61.54; H, 4.27 per cent). The alcoholic mother-liquor was completely evaporated and the residue repeatedly extracted with petroleum ether whence a mixture, m.p. 95°-100°, was obtained. After crystallisation from dilute alcohol (twice) and four successive crystallisations from hot petroleum ether, a substance, m.p. 121°-22° (0.03 g.) was obtained. (Found C, 61.15; H, 4.65. $C_{12}H_{10}O_5$ requires C, 61.54; H, 4.27 per cent). The foregoing methylmethoxycoumarin carboxylate (0.4 g.) was heated for a few seconds with concentrated sulphuric acid (3.5 c.c.), the colour of the solution changed from yellowish green to brownish green. After cooling, the solution was decomposed by pouring over crushed ice. The separated solids crystallised from hot dilute alcohol, m.p. 251-52°. (Found: C, 58.40; H, 3.3. $C_{10}H_8O_5$ requires C, 58.25; H, 2.9 per cent). The substance gave

(a) deep violet colour with ferric chloride, (b) decomposed sodium bicarbonate and (c) an ice-cold dilute solution in sodium hydroxide showed a yellowish green fluorescence which faded very quickly (cf. 7-hydroxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid which gave deep blue fluorescence under the same conditions).

The foregoing acid (0.6 g.) was heated in an oil-bath at 260° for 4-5 hours. The product was treated with very dilute solution of sodium bicarbonate, washed and the residue crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 225°. It was identified as 5-hydroxycoumarin by mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen. Therefore the methoxymethyl ester, m.p. 121-22°, was 5-methoxy-6-carbomethoxycoumarin.

7-Methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid.—The methoxy methyl ester, m.p. 172° (0.5 g.) was heated with sodium hydroxide solution (7 c.c. of 10%) till complete solution was obtained. After cooling in ice, the solution was acidified with excess of hydrochloric acid and the mixture boiled for a few minutes. The precipitate was crystallised from acetic acid, m.p. 274°. (Found: C, 60.36; H, 3.4. $C_{11}H_8O_5$ requires C, 60.0; H, 3.69 per cent).

The *chloride* of the above acid (4 g.) was prepared with thionyl chloride (80 c.c.) by heating for 1 hour. After removal of the unreacted thionyl chloride *in vacuo*, the residue crystallised from hot dry toluene, m.p. 190-91°. (Found: C, 56.68; H, 3.59. $C_{11}H_7O_4Cl$ requires C, 55.46; H, 2.94 per cent). Ethyl ester prepared after interaction of the chloride with alcohol had m. p. 147-48°. (Found: C, 63.06; H, 5.18. $C_{13}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 62.9; H, 4.84 per cent). The *amide* had m.p. 297-98° after crystallisation from 33% alcohol. (Found: N, 6.52. $C_{11}H_9O_4N$ requires N, 6.39 per cent).

Condensation of 7-Methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic Chloride with Sodioethylisopropyl Malonate: Formation of (IV, R = COOC₂H₅).—Sodio ethylisopropyl malonate prepared in dry toluene (2.1 g. ethylisopropyl malonate, sodium powder 2.5 g.) was heated with the acid chloride (2.4 g.) at 115-120° under pressure for 4-5 hours. The precipitated solids were found to be a mixture of sodium chloride and sodium salt of 7-methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid formed by hydrolysis. The toluene filtrate gave a solid on removal of the solvent. After repeated washing with petroleum ether, the substance was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 141-42°. (Found: C, 62.4, 63.0; H, 4.83, 5.6. $C_{21}H_{24}O_8$ requires C, 62.37; H, 5.94 per cent). The above substance could not be hydrolysed to the related dicarboxylic (or a monocarboxylic) acid as it hydrolysed to 7-methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid.

The similar condensation with ethyl-sodio α -bromomalonate gave two substances of unknown constitution which were separated by the solubility of one in petroleum ether. The petroleum ether-soluble substance crystallised from dilute acetic acid and had m.p. 55°. (Found: C, 53.38; H, 6.29 per cent.). From the insoluble portion, hot carbon tetrachloride removed the other product which had m.p. 140°, after crystallisation from alcohol. (Found: C, 62.42; H, 4.94 per cent). The nature of these products is still under investigation.

Since ω -cyanoacetate resacetophenone dimethyl ether (Sonn, *Ber.*, 1918, 51, 823) (2 g.) was smoothly converted by demethylation and elimination of hydrogen cyanide (or by the elimination of acetonitrile) at room temperature (30°), when dissolved in sulphuric acid (10 c.c.) and left for 2 hours, into 6-methoxycoumaranone, the possibility of

similar ring-closure in IV ($R=CN$) was investigated. The condensation of ethyl *iso*-propyl cyanacetate and the chloride of 7-methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid was carried out as described in the case of *isopropyl* malonic ester derivative with the difference that the temperature was maintained at 130° . The residue from toluene was crystallised from alcohol and had m.p. 156° . [Found : C, 64.25 ; H, 5.37 ; N, 3.98. $C_{15}H_{13}O_6N$ (IV, $R=CN$) requires C, 63.86 ; H, 5.32 ; N, 3.92 per cent]. The substance (1 g.) in sulphuric acid (5 c.c.), left for 12 hours at room temperature and then for 2 hours at $40-50^{\circ}$ gave a substance after decomposition with ice which crystallised from hot benzene and had m.p. $258-60^{\circ}$. (Found : C, 59.79 ; H, 3.99 per cent). This substance is not the coumaranone derivative expected. It degraded to 7-methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid when treated with ammoniacal silver nitrate.

Reaction of the Chloride of 7-Methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic Acid with isoButyl Zinc iodide.—The acid chloride (6 g.) suspended in dry toluene (10 g.) was treated with *iso*-butyl zinc iodide (prepared from 15 g. of *isobutyl* iodide) in toluene. After standing in ice for 2 hours and then at room temperature (30°) for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hours, the mixture was decomposed with ice and hydrochloric acid. The residue from toluene was washed free from 7-methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid with sodium bicarbonate solution and was treated with ether. The ethereal solution furnished a product which after crystallisation from petroleum ether had m.p. $87-89^{\circ}$. (Found : C, 65.49 ; H, 6.2. $C_{15}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 65.21 ; H, 5.8 per cent). A mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of *isobutyl* ester of 7-methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid (m.p. $99-101^{\circ}$) was $87-90^{\circ}$.

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EXPERIMENTS ON THE SYNTHESIS OF OREOSELONE. PART II.

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ω -Chlororesacetophenone condenses with ethyl acetoacetate to give 6-chloroacetyl-7-hydroxycoumarin which is transformed to the related furanocoumarin. But alkylation of this substance proved difficult. It, however, condenses with acetone to give a monomolecular condensation product. ω -Chlororesacetophenone also condenses with oxaloacetic ester and the product has been converted into the related furanocoumarin and condensed with acetone.

Clayton (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 2016) found that a nitro, carboxyl, carboethoxyl and acetyl group in the *meta* position of a phenol molecule prevented Pechmann reaction taking place with a β -ketonic ester although Shah, Sethna, Bannerjee and Chakravarti (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1937, 14, 714) found that β -methyl resorcylic acid condensed with ethyl acetoacetate. It has been found that β -resorcylic acid condensed with malic acid (Part I, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23365) to give simultaneously a 7-hydroxy- and a 5-hydroxycoumarin derivative. It has now been found that ω -chlororesacetophenone condenses with ethyl acetoacetate to give (I, $R=Me$) in poor yield. The condensation